

THE CONCEPT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the concept of digital transformation, its significance and benefits in education, international experience, as well as the implementation of new innovative approaches through digital technologies in the Uzbekistan education system, the enhancement of traditional methods, and the adaptation of the knowledge delivery system to modern requirements.*

Keywords: *digital transformation in education, digital technologies, students and teachers, opportunity, information and communication technologies, online and hybrid education.*

Annotatsiya. *Bu maqolada raqamli transformatsiya tushunchasi, uning ta'limdagi ahamiyati va afzalliklari, jahon tajribasi hamda uning O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida raqamli texnologiyalar orqali yangi innovatsion yondashuvlarni joriy qilish, an'anaviy uslublarni takomillashtirish va bilim berish tizimini zamonaviy talablarga moslashtirish tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli transformatsiya ta'lim, raqamli texnologiyalar, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar, imkoniyat, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, Onlayn va gibrid ta'lim.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируется концепция цифровой трансформации, ее значение и преимущества в сфере образования, международный опыт, а также внедрение новых инновационных подходов посредством цифровых технологий в систему образования Узбекистана, совершенствование традиционных методов и адаптация системы передачи знаний к современным требованиям.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая трансформация в образовании, цифровые технологии, студенты и преподаватели, возможности, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, онлайн и гибридное обучение.*

Introduction. In the current era of globalization and technology, the education system is rapidly undergoing digitalization. Digital transformation is having a profound impact not only on the economy and industry but also on education. The effective use of digital technologies in the education system enables the learning process to become high-quality and innovative.

Today, on a global scale, digital transformation is of great significance in various fields, including the education system [1]. The digitalization of the educational process creates new opportunities for students and teachers and serves to enhance teaching methods. Digital transformation is the process of developing and automating various spheres of society using information technologies. This process encompasses the introduction of new innovative approaches through digital technologies, the improvement of traditional methods, and the adaptation of the knowledge transfer system to meet modern requirements.

Many countries are reforming their education systems through digital transformation:

Finland - Interactive and digital learning tools have been widely implemented.

Singapore - The education system is managed based on artificial intelligence and data analytics.

The USA and European countries - MOOC platforms and hybrid education models are extensively utilized [2].

Digital transformation encompasses the following areas:

Utilization of information and communication technologies;

Development of online and hybrid educational models;

Implementation of distance learning platforms;

Application of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality.

Digital transformation in the field of education has several key priorities:

Enhancing the quality and effectiveness of education

Digital transformation is impacting the education system in various ways:

Personalization of the learning process - Each student will have the opportunity to select a curriculum tailored to their individual abilities and needs.

Interactive learning through digital technologies - Simulations, virtual laboratories, and interactive platforms make the educational process more engaging and effective.

Accessibility of information resources - Numerous distance learning platforms (such as Coursera, edX, Khan Academy, Udemy) provide access to the world's best lessons on a global scale.

In recent years, the demand for distance learning has grown significantly. This trend accelerated markedly during the pandemic period. Currently, the following platforms are being widely utilized:

MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) - Massive Open Online Courses

LMS (Learning Management System) - Learning Management Systems (Google Classroom, Moodle, Blackboard)

Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) - The opportunity to study scientific experiments and laboratory exercises remotely [3]

Digital technologies create opportunities for effective organization of the learning process. For example, personalized educational methods can be implemented through artificial intelligence and analytical tools. This helps to develop curricula tailored to each student's individual abilities and needs.

Distance education and equal opportunities for all

Digital transformation is making education globally accessible. Through the Internet and digital platforms, learners will have the opportunity to receive education remotely. This is especially important for those living in remote areas or those with limited access to traditional education.

Interactive and innovative learning methods

Unlike traditional educational approaches, digital transformation enables the use of virtual laboratories, simulations, gamification, and VR/AR (virtual and augmented reality) technologies. This helps make the learning process engaging and interactive.

New opportunities for future teachers

Digital transformation plays a crucial role in the professional growth and enhancement of teachers' pedagogical skills [5]. For example, online courses, webinars, and digital educational resources create opportunities for teachers to continuously improve their knowledge and competencies.

Conclusion. Digital transformation will radically change the sphere of education, allowing the introduction of new innovative approaches. This process creates opportunities for

improving the quality of education at all levels, personalizing the educational process, and widely using educational resources. Therefore, the correct direction of the integration of digital technologies into education and their effective use is one of the urgent tasks of today. Digital transformation is fundamentally changing the field of education, and its effective implementation serves to improve the quality of education.

For the successful implementation of digital transformation in the education system of Uzbekistan:

- Improving online educational platforms;
- Expanding the hybrid education model;
- Implementing innovative educational technologies;
- Developing teachers' digital competencies are necessary.

These measures will significantly contribute to the more effective implementation of the digital transformation process and enhancement of education quality.

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